

The Effects of Socialization on Employee Commitment at Workplace

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Abstract

This study examines corporate socializing and employee loyalty at k-executive electric. Multiple factors, including interpersonal relationships, compensation, personality attributes, and professional progression, were found to influence employee loyalty. Socialization is believed to positively improve employees' affective, ongoing, and normative commitment. These links were evaluated using the information of 371 K Electric executives. In addition, questionnaires were used to collect information. Statistical software known as SPSS was utilized to evaluate the data. According to the research, characteristics such as coworker relationships, remuneration, personality, and advancement significantly affect employee commitment. In order to increase employee loyalty, a company must prioritize strengthening social bonds.

Keywords: Commitment, Socialization, Coworker relation, Pay, Promotion and Employee commitment.

Introduction

Researches show that employee commitment means psychological and physical involvement in the organization. It also well-defined as the strength of individual identification immersion in an organization. Employee commitment plays a very imperative part in achieving the goals of the association. The definition provides distinct components of employee commitment. An imperative progress in academic study is the recognition that employees can stay committed to various unlike work-related foci. Current work recommends the position of seeing objects of commitment in adding to the organization himself, for example supervisors or change initiatives (Herscovitch & Meyer, 2002). Strong confidence and belief besides acceptance of organization goal, on the behalf of organization self-motivation, willingness, and a strong desire to preserve involvement. Those who are committed to the organization at the individual level they must experience job satisfaction and a low-pressure level. if we talk about the impact of socialization on the commitment of employees at the workplace, the procedure starts when employees apply for the occupation. In that process, both employees and organizations are new and unknown from their qualities. They need time and a proper way by which they could know each other. This official process is known as socialization. It is the method that can impact the commitment level. Socialization besides employee commitment has been through empirical observation established by several researchers.

Socialization provides employees related information because new employees are more socialized and committed at work. Now a day's companies are forming aliens. The exertion stress of employees also said to increase, this might affect the commitment of the employee. The commitment of employees is influenced by several factors like pay, promotion, coworker relation, and job dimension. Each employee has changed pay satisfaction, satisfied individuals will give positive response whereas those who are not, will show a negative response. They demonstrate lower work performance, more demand, high turnover, and reduced job satisfaction. Pay is a major motivator for employees' satisfaction at work. Employees feel satisfied and give their best when they felt they received the desired salary. Pay satisfaction well-defined as per conformity between individual observation of income essentially received and of pay ideally received. If the individual finds that his or her perception of pay imitates conforms with the actual pay received, would be satisfied by it. It is imperative to realize whether the organizational commitment is a sentiment that is open to involvement by

the organization. Socialization states the procedure by which an individual gets the customs, beliefs, values, attitudes, and language characteristics of an organization.

An individual sense is created by loyalty like it is the right thing to do so they “ought” to stay committed to the connection. Along with means of understanding the bases of assurance, research on the efforts of employee commitment is to construct the understanding. If employees see themselves as an important referent, then they might make solid commitments to administrators and coworkers. The employee has the strongest immediate influence on employee attitudes and their subsequent behaviors. Becker’s (1992) research inveterate several hypotheses by showing employees do make significant differences among the organization, and managers and colleagues once it comes to various of commitment.

Around there has stood a great transaction of literature that examines the organizational socialization method and its effects on workers' job adjustment, organizational advancement, and retention. this study is aimed.

Literature Review

Socialization and Employee Commitment

Individuals acquire the customs also performance in ways that are accurate and desirable for organization that is very important. But then this doesn’t occur through itself and managers are answerable for accomplishing this. Socialization is the one primary phase (syatat, 2006). By way of, socialization consists of elementary rationalization besides

Overview of employees and training new employees about the organization’s culture, the goal line for newcomers in their initial days are:

- Acquire the knowledge of goals, rules, and dealings of organization
- Becoming acquainted by approximately rules and regulations for instance payroll, recruitment, benefits, and overtime pay.
- Learning innovative duties and responsibilities.
- Meeting associated employees (syatat, 2006)

The idea of this concept, the workplace commitment has involved the attention of researchers and experts for more than half a century. Various descriptions of commitment have been accessible, but then again it is well acknowledged that commitment imitates feelings for example attachment, ID, or devotion to the commitment’s objective (Morrow & P.C, 1983). To understand commitment researchers naturally sought alternative ways and in theory and practices pinpoint its contribution in both. To characterize commitment as a multidimensional concept is one of the important alternate approaches. Suggestions to this effect had been made in earlier research (Rotondi et al.,1975). As a whole, Employee commitment states to a worker’s part and identification through the organization. Commitment is the mark of devotion experienced through the teams linked to the bonding by the organization, and the willingness to continue employed by it. More, employee commitment is well-defined as a strength that binds an individual towards a target besides to a passage of act appropriate to that target. There are three dimensions of commitment, namely, affective “emotive part”, normative “honest compulsion” and continuance “consciousness of the costs linked by terminating membership” (Herscovitch & Meyer, 2001). So, the one who stay with organization is the features of a committed employee through thick and thin, be present at work habitually, keeps firm’s assets and shares company’s goals.

Employees committed to modification hard work are added probable to acquire from the procedure. Devoted employees want to pay back to besides get the outcomes of their exertions, and employees can organize thus concluded knowledge (Teare & Rayner, 2002).

Once they study since actuality intricate in a company’s transformation, employee deliberate that knowledge is mark achievement of execution. The psychological attachment of labors to their works states to employee commitment (Allen & Meyer, 1990). When the organization members have strong commitment then worker and organization both gain benefits. Employees might be extra suitable to take mutually extrinsic rewards, for instance payments and benefits, and psychological rewards in the form of greater job satisfaction if they have high level of commitment to organization (Mowday, Steers, & Poter, 1973). Commitment value in organization because employee tardiness, absenteeism, and turnover will be reduced by this. (Cotton & Tuttle, 1986).

Considerable suggestion across an inclusive samples and performance varieties indicators recommends that worker with solid commitment to company will be more valued worker than those with weak commitment.

The Coworker relation also has the ability to create a working environment a wish or an unlikable place to spend. Number of studies done before on community support at the office, in actual focused on superintendent support. Coworkers' connection in association is a kind of personal relationship which is constructed on two ideas: the relationship of leader-member and interaction of coworkers. Some of the major theories connecting to interpersonal relation is which an organization contain:

1. Interpersonal relationship
2. Three-dimensional theory
3. Social exchange theory, and the a-b-x theory.

Above all these the social exchange theory has remained revised more than a few whiles, which deliberates the front-runner participant relationship is not just the connection among the upright duo but then again connection among the coworker's horizontal pair coworkers, further groups, and even the whole organization. Therefore, many researchers in recent years have long-drawn-out the studies scope (Uhl-bien, Graen, & Kao, 1992; 2008). Social relationships of the workplace may create a vital input to employees' job contentment, wellbeing and efficiency. In the current studies though, places its prominence on employee observations of co-worker, the coworkers that employees are continually in connection by on a day-to-day basis in a transaction industry.

Coworker discuss co-workers at the bottom of one another in their daily jobs at what time requisite by means of giving out data and know-how over and above provided that support and stipulation. considerable rewards for case payment, promotion and power over the policy would increase apparent support. Co-worker can likewise give or else fail to give a basis for unity and unified confrontation to management. All along by this co-worker has very important affects outside the work place (Fiedler, 1997) think the amity, acceptance, and members of a group is coworker's relationship devotion built up between them, which also refers to the level of the subordinates' self-assurance, faith, and respect in their leaders (Chen, 1989). According to (Tsao, 1990) research indicated that the excellence of the coworkers' relationship reveals the efficiency of statement among the two parties, as well as a symbol of how well the two parties match up with one another. Coworkers' behaviors also influence the relationship of coworkers. The aforementioned study similarly designated that work pleasure has an optimistic connection to the front-runner-associate relationship and how fit the coworkers organize with one additional; the improved the coordinating connection among the influential and assistants, the high the work gratification rate would stay. Meanwhile the method of the employees in the service industry affects customers' perceptions to the quality of the service, service-oriented businesses have to look for method of effective management. Trust is a primary element in management. When a manager is trustable for his subordinate and interact on good term with his manager, he would take the damages and more willing experienced from the behaviors of the coworkers because subordinate believes that he has never ignored the right (Lin & Lin, 2006).

Promotions and Employee Commitment

Imperative organizations are the one who recognize the features of HR practices that perform essential roles or have superior effect in enhancing the commitment of employees. Promotion is one of such boosters of commitment. Movement inside an association to position in which tasks and apparently status increased is usually measured as promotion. Promotion potential impact the behavior in organization also inspires people to superior capabilities to change ahead (Parry et al., 2009). Promotion is worn as prize and incentive to enhanced effort and extra logistically permitted forms of performances. Employee willpower effort tougher if he feels that will main to the upgrade. If they feel that enhanced jobs are reserved for outsider that is a little incentive for them (Pearce & Poulston, 2011). The arrangement of promotion approve organization to bout its necessity for skilled workers with the workers wish to put on the skills have develop in employees. (Gomez, 2002). There is an important association among opportunity for progression and job satisfactions at high level. An effective system of job promotion can better managerially result efficiency and employee's confidence at high level (Prasad et al., 2001).

Accordingly, Armstrong (2006) to the goal of work promotion process of corporation ought to stay permit administration to get the best ability attainable inside company to seal further superior posts and to make available workers by the chance to verve onward towards their professions in the corporation, in agreement with the chance obtainable and their personal capabilities. Furthermost persons have a call for high assessment of their selves and sense that what did they must remain known by means of others anxious (Richard & Johnson, 2001). Employee growth is a promotion's strategy and as a reward for good presentation also considered and employee capabilities recognition (Samuel & Chipunza, 2009). legislature who had work completion had an outgoing impact on worker obligation as did those with higher levels of pay, feeling secure in one's work, considering the work was hard work and thinking the management were great. Feeling dissatisfied with one's pay was related. The study exposed the optimistic relation between promotion and employee commitment.

It brings a in heigh worth in worker preservation as a vibrant sequence strategy retains the worker provoked to have up a virtuous presentation and long-standing assurance with the corporation. Job promotion among the existing workers also creates a sense of security. "Promotion is a shifting of employee for an activity of better importance and better payment". (Lazear, 2000)

Promotion is worn as a praise for higher worker work presentation and managerially authorized shape of performance. People will work harder in the event that they sense that this could be the source of their promotion.

Pay and Employee Commitment

Current research has initiated that worker commitment is a multifaceted concept made up of a selection of elements. though job and managerial satisfaction and corporate arrogance are necessary facets of pledge, a host of pays and benefits have an impact on whether workers remain truly committed to their boss. To completely realize the idea of pay agreement, it is essential to assess study on the theory. From the initiation of managerial science, payment has stood well-thought-out a vital recompense to inspire the performance of employees (Naylor, 1911). So far it was not up until thinkers started discovering equality in societal contacts (Adam & j.s, 1963) that the definite perceptive instruments over which payment inspires employees started to develop clear. Quickly next, managerial scientists assumed that approach of fairmindedness lead to association applicable insolences such as work approval (Locke & E.A, 1969) and, more specially, payment fulfillment, and those arrogances effect worker actions in organization (Farell & Stamm; Judge & Bono; Scott & Taylor; Tett & Meyer, 1988; 2001; 1985; 1993). First research relied upon equity on pay satisfaction (Adams, 1963) and inconsistency concepts (Lawler, 1971) to give details in what way persons decide pay satisfaction. Global is treated build in the models, pay pleasure to engage in certain behavior motivates individuals, but these approaches do not state which to choose as a behavior.

One of the basic conditions to satisfy employment and at work fulfil these human needs organization is financial reward that is, earnings and salaries which is pay and also including benefits. Wages is pay that worker receive or obtain for work done. Meanwhile, benefits can be distinct as any form of compensation other than wages and salary that provided by association. The workers tend to express pledge when there is an add to in wages and benefits. Through pay and benefits that provided by boss, worker become more motivates and directly increases their level of pledge. In addition, wages also is a measure in order to determine the employees' commitment level to the association and it is needed as means of satisfying and meeting the needs of workers.

Personality and Employee Commitment

Personality model Big Five imply the character be made up of five comparatively traits of independent which provide a significant the study explanation differences of individual (Kumar, Bakhshi, & Rani, 2009) and response. Five scopes in personality Big Five model are Extroversion, Conscientiousness, experience openness, Cordiality and Neurosis. The Big Five character of each is a set of traits which inclined together to occur individuals.

Extroversion is state of actuality main concerned and what is outside from satisfaction obtain. Behavioral tendency measures by using issue are sociable, outgoing, self-confident, talkative, and lively (Barrick et al., 1991). Meticulousness tendency to show self-control refers, perform obediently and goal focused on. This behavioral tendency includes similar being hard working, success-oriented, inflexible, watchful, and accountable. General approval is honesty to experience for art, sentiment, adventure, imagination and skills with some variety. The behavioral tendencies linked with Openness to Experience include being creative, refined, inquisitive, unique, broad minded, intelligent (Digman & M., 1990). It also reflects the need for variety, aesthetic compassion, and eccentric values (McCrae, R., John, & P., 1992). Amicability refers to a tendency to be sympathetic and supportive. This factor includes behavioral tendencies like being polite, bendable, trusting, good-natured, supportive, forgiving, soft-hearted, and broadminded (Barrick et al., 1991).

Neurosis states negative emotion to the tendency to experience like irritation, nervousness, or person's depression. Its state emotional instability. It is linked with behavioral tendency factors include being nervous, unhappy, annoyed, uncomfortable, emotive, concerned, and self-doubting (Barrick et al., 1991). Personality is a complicated psychological build used to find out about the people's behavior, and in general, various human behaviors in different situations. Different classifications have been presented for personality extent. McCrae and Costa developed a five-factor model. According to this model, personality is divided into various five extent, counting neuroticism (tendency to experience anxiety, tension, hostility, shyness, irrational thinking, depression, and low self-confidence), sociability (tendency to attend to the external world, care for other people, and enjoy interaction with others), openness to experience (active search of using the others' experience and longing for curiosity, appreciation of art, imagination, open-mindedness, and innovation), amicability (tendency to respect others and agree with them), meticulousness (ability to organize, stability, control and motivation in targeted behaviors and tendency toward competency, discipline, attempt for improvement, restrain, and contemplation). According to this model, there is a specific approach in every being and nature toward the responsibilities and objectives of the organization depending on his/her own personality traits. therefore, sources of imagination can be the source personality differences of the people, progress, or source of many managerial problems and it can also affect their behavior, repetition, choices, and managerial behavior. Since personality character are considered as factors to decide the people's behavior, their recognition can help provide a structure to predict behavior. In fact, knowledge about the personality of people can assist the manager of association to appoint qualified persons in different managerial positions in order to decrease staff income and to increase their managerial commitment.

Problem Statement

Organizational socialization is defined as "the process by which an individual acquires the values, skills, anticipated behaviors, and social knowledge necessary to assume an organizational function and participate as a member of the organization." The objective of this study is to determine how socializing influences employee commitment to a company. Multiple outcomes, including interactions with coworkers, compensation, personality traits, and professional advancement, have been connected to employee socialization. In this study of socialization, organizations are investigated in considerable depth. There is no way to overestimate the significance of employee loyalty. Difficulties related to early socializing in contemporary studies, behavioral data is overemphasized. The objective is to identify the undesirable aspects of employee socialization through worker participation. By analyzing this data, this study seeks to determine the effect of socializing on employee loyalty.

Research Significance

This research will help in recognizing those variables that strongly effect employee commitment in organization. it's a new topic for research in Pakistan. Observing in the direction of all research studies done in Pakistan, it is observed that there is irrelevant research done in Pakistan and it has formed a wide gap, which requirements to be filled up through the current and the upcoming. Additionally, this research may be a means of access for different researcher who want to conduct this study.

Hypothesis

- Coworker relation has a positive effect on employee commitment.
- Pay has a positive effect on employee commitment.
- Personality has a positive effect on employee commitment
- Promotion has a positive effect on employee commitment.

Methodology

Research Design

The investigate plan may be a successive and coherent arrange for interfacing empirical information with research objectives, which makes a difference in drawing conclusion (Yin, 2007). The research plan for this venture is quantitative and descriptive in nature. The chapter also delivers a description of in what way study variables will be measured; how statistics will be examined and obtainable.

Variables

In this study we are using quantitative research. Its templates are objective, elaborate, and various times, even investigational. Logical, statistical, and unbiased results are achieved from this research method. Data collection happened using and conducted a structured method and larger samples that represent the entire population.

Research Approach

There are two types of research approach.

1. Deductive
2. Inductive

Inductive Approach

It is beginning with a set of empirical observations, in search of patterns in those observations, and then theorizing about those patterns.

Deductive Approach

It starts with a hypothesis, creating theories from that hypothesis, and after that gathering and analyzing information to test those hypotheses.

Since in this project a conceptual system constructed on the writing and hypothesis has been created which was at that point tried by assembling the reactions of the respondent, and the conclusion were drawn from the experimentally tested hypotheses, subsequently it falls within the sort of deductive approach.

Sampling Techniques

There are two sampling techniques categories. Probability and non-probability sampling. In probability sampling, respondents are arbitrarily chosen to require part in a study or other mode of inquire about. Non-probability testing is when a test is made through a non-random handle. This seems incorporate a analyst sending a study connect to their companions or ceasing individuals on the street. For large population just like the one utilized within the ponder, it is inconceivable to choose randomly respondents subsequently non-probability sampling has been utilized for this research.

Sample Size

Sample size may be a parcel of components drawn from the populace, which is examined with the presumption it will have the same characteristic as the investigate population (Goddard, 2004). The total population of K Electric is 10,500 so the sample size is 371. At 95% and 5% of error margin. The calculation of sample size for this study has been calculated through software Rao Soft.

Data Collection

The study depends on main data that was composed by means of a semi structured questionnaire. The questionnaire is organized into different segments to capture data on employee commitment, coworker relation, pay, personality and promotion. Once the respondents had been recognized, questionnaires were circulated through social media to collect data from K Electric employees.

Data Collection Instrument

The construct is based on the instrument used for this research study, which have well-known reliabilities. The survey for this study comprised of two parts. First part is demographic section that is based on nominal scale. Second part is related to the used variables in this study, which are based on five Point Likert Scale.

Data Analysis Method

In this research Reliability Analysis, Descriptive Statistics, Correlation Analysis, Multiple Regression and Simple Regression Analysis is used to test the results of this study through

S.no	Variables	Items	Citation
1	Employee Commitment	4	(Bozeman, Dennis, & Perrewe, 2001)
2	Coworker Relation	4	(Mossholder, W., Settoon, & Henagan, 2005) (Kammeyer-Mueller, D., & Wanberg, 2003) (Susskind & M., 2003)
3	Pay	4	(Edwards & R., 2006) (Koh, Christine, Ang, & Straub, 2004) (Heilman M., 2004)
4	Promotion	4	(Alba, Richard, Rumbaut, & Marotz, 2005) (Maertz, P., Jr., & Campion, 2004) (Jiang, J., & Klein, 2002)
5	Personality	4	(human, J., & biesanz, 2011) (Radel, Remi, Pelletier, & Sarrazin, 2011) (Fast, A., & Funder, 2008)

Results and Discussion

A conceptual framework was developed which shows coworker relation, personality, pay and promotion effect on employee commitment. In methodology, how objective of the study will be achieved discussed in detail. This chapter focuses on results and discussion of the study discoveries as made by the instruments used during the research activity (i.e., questionnaires). Furthermore, this chapter includes Descriptive Analysis, Reliability Analysis, Correlation Analysis and regression Analysis.

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive analysis is undertaking for measure the univariate normality, in table 1 the results is shown.

Table 1
Descriptive Statistics

Construct	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Employee Commitment	371	11.70	3.10	.140	-.050
Coworker Relation	371	11.59	3.20	.300	.051
Pay	371	11.85	3.09	.033	-.205
Personality	371	11.64	3.17	.286	.037
Promotion	371	12.10	2.60	.147	-.508

Table 1 result suggest that coworker relation (Mean=11.59, SD=3.20) has the highest skewness that is (SK=0.300) and pay (Mean=11.85, SD=3.09) has the lowest skewness that is (SK= 0.033). Moreover, the highest kurtosis is for promotion (KT= -0.508) with a (Mean= 12.10, SD= 2.60) and the lowest kurtosis is for personality (KT= -0.037) with a (Mean= 11.64, SD= 3.17). the value of skewness and kurtosis lie between ± 3.5 , thus, as the data fulfill univariate normality criteria.

Reliability Analysis

Reliability analysis is used to analyze internal consistency through Cronbach alpha. Results are shown in table 2.

Table 2
Reliability Analysis

Construct	Mean	Standard Deviation	Cronbach's Alpha
Employee Commitment	11.70	3.10	.720
Coworker Relation	11.59	3.20	.691
Pay	11.85	3.09	.678
Personality	11.64	3.17	.681
Promotion	12.10	2.60	.845

Table 2 shows the highest Cronbach's alpha value is for promotion ($\alpha = .845$, mean= 12.10, SD= 2.60) and the lowest is for pay ($\alpha = .678$, mean= 11.85, SD 3.09) as all the value are greater than 0.60 Cronbach's alpha, hence construct can be considered reliable.

Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis is used to evaluate the strength of relationship between two quantitative variables by statistical method. And to analyze, whether the variables are unique and distinctive. Result is shown in table 3.

Table 3
Correlation Analysis

Construct	Employee Commitment	Coworker Relation	Pay	Personality	Promotion
Employee Commitment	1				
Coworker Relation	.615	1			
Pay	.362	.322	1		
Personality	.632	.955	.498	1	
Promotion	.483	.544	.616	.846	1

Table 3 shows the highest correlation ($r = 0.955$) is between the pair of personality (mean= 11.64, SD= 3.17) and the coworker relation (Mean=11.59, SD=3.20) and the lowest correlation ($r = .322$) is between the pay (Mean=11.85, SD=3.09) and coworker relation (Mean=11.59, SD=3.20) as all the values are in between the range of 0.30 to 0.90 then they are in acceptable range

Regression Analysis

Regression analysis is used to test the overall model that the predictors (coworker relation, pay, personality and promotion) have an impact on employee commitment. Results are shown in table 4.

Table 4
Regression Result

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	3.405	.695		4.902	.000
	Coworker Relation	.113	.131	.117	.863	.009
	Pay	.036	.041	.035	.860	.030
	Personality	.488	.132	.499	3.700	.000
	Promotion	.076	.033	.093	2.297	.022

Dependent variable: employee commitment $R^2 = 0.410$ adjusted $R^2 = 0.404$, $P = 0 < 0.05$. The result shows that the predictors (coworker relation, pay, personality and promotion) aggregately explain 60.4% of the variance. The construct it was also initiate that coworker relation ($\beta = .113$, $P > 0.05$) pay ($\beta = .036$, $P > 0.05$) personality ($\beta = .488$, $P > 0.05$) and promotion ($\beta = .076$, $P > 0.05$) the establish model clarifies the effect of coworker relation, personality, pay and promotion which is obvious from the following regression equation. Employee commitment = $3.405 + .113$ coworker relation + $.036$ pay + $.488$ personality + $.076$ promotion + $.695$.

Hypothesis 1: Coworker Relation and Employee Commitment

The hypothesis state that coworker relation positively effect employee commitment, result is presented in table 5.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	4.811	.477		10.081	.000
	Coworker Relation	.595	.040	.615	14.990	.000

Dependent variable: employee commitment $R^2 = 0.378$ adjusted $R^2 = 0.377$, $P = 0 > 0.05$. Regression result show the coworker relation explain 37.7% of the variance. It indicates that coworker relation ($\beta = .615$, $p > 0.05$) has a significant and positive effect on employee commitment. The regression equation is Employee commitment = $4.811 + .595$ coworker relation + $.477$.

Hypothesis 2: Pay and Employee Commitment

The hypothesis state that pays positively affect employee commitment. Result are presented in table 6.

		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardize d Coefficients	t	Sig.
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	9.783	.631		15.513	.000
	Pay	.362	.051	.359	3.151	.002

Dependent variable: employee commitment $R^2 = 0.206$ adjusted $R^2 = 0.204$, $P = 0 > 0.05$.

Regression result show the pay explain 20.4% of the variance. It indicates that pay ($\beta = .362$, $p > 0.05$) has a positive and significant effect on employee commitment.

The regression equation is Employee commitment = 9.783+ .162 pay +.631

Hypothesis 3: Personality and Employee Commitment

The hypothesis state that Personality positively affects employee commitment. Result are presented in table 7.

		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardize d Coefficients	t	Sig.
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.511	.476		9.473	.000
	Personality	.618	.039	.632	15.658	.000

Dependent variable: employee commitment $R^2 = 0.399$ adjusted $R^2 = 0.398$, $P = 0 > 0.05$. Regression result show the personality explain 39.8% of the variance. It indicates that personality ($\beta = .632$, $p > 0.05$) has a positive and significant effect on employee commitment.

The regression equation is Employee commitment = 4,511+ .618 personality +.476.

Hypothesis 4: Promotion and Employee Commitment

The hypothesis state that Promotion positively effect employee commitment., result is presented in table 8.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	9.975	.508		19.624	.000
	Promotion	.476	.042	.483	3.584	.000

Dependent variable: employee commitment $R^2 = 0.304$ adjusted $R^2 = 0.301$, $P = 0 > 0.05$. Regression result show the promotion explain 30.1% of the variance. It indicates that promotion ($\beta = .483$, $p > 0.05$) has a positive and significant effect on employee commitment.

The regression equation is Employee commitment = $9.975 + .476$ promotion + $.508$.

Discussion

The hypothesis stating that predictors (co-worker relation, pay, personality, promotion) have combined effect on Employee Commitment was accepted (Refer to Table 4). This result is reliable to past studies, which also initiate that that socialization effects employee commitment.

The hypothesis 1 stating that the predictor co-worker relation positively effects Employee Commitment was also accepted (Refer to Table 5). Study found that in workplace building relation is an important aspect of the commitment of employees. Employees commit to their work if they feel strong co-worker relation. It is also found from past studies that coworker relation positively effects employee commitment and results show that co-worker relation is acceptable and significant effect on employee commitment.

Hypothesis 2 stating that the predictor pay relation positively effect employee commitment accepted (Refer to table 6). Study found that pay has a main role in organizations which directly influence employee commitment. A good pay is always a key of strong employee commitment. It is proved by the results that pay is acceptable and significant impact on employee commitment.

Hypothesis 3 stating that the predictor personality positively effect employee performance (Refer to table 7). Personality is something that effects employees in a positive way personality defines you your action, your existence, it is proved by the results that personality is acceptable and significant effect on employee performance.

Hypothesis 4 stating that predictor promotion is positively impact employee performance was accepted (Refer to Table 8). The result of hypothesis tests for promotion has an impact on employee performance and have significant influence. So, with the promoted employees keen to work tough and wish to attain extreme work result, can progress its performance effectively. Therefore, it can be said that appropriateness of promotion of situations will impact the fulfilment so that the performance of employees will rise.

Conclusion

Summarizing entire research findings, gives conclusion and provide recommendation, future research of the impact of socialization on employee commitment of the employees of K-electric.

The overall perception of respondent towards the socialization (coworker relation, personality, pay and promotion) of the organization shows the majority of respondents have satisfied in their perception towards the socialization of the K-electric. The reaction of the respondent towards the socialization in the K electric entails the majority of employees feel that coworker relation pay personality and promotion is positively exist in their organization which reflect the good employee commitment.

Outcomes from co relation analysis point it out that them exist a positive and significant relationship among the socialization and employee commitment based on the results we can argue that socialization has an effect on employee commitment. Result from regression result shows that 60.4% of variance that explain the employee commitment of K electric employees in terms of independent variable i.e., coworker relation, personality, pay and promotion. The multicollinearity test reveal that there is no multicollinearity. Following conclusion are made which is based on. The aim of the study was exploring the impact of socialization on employee commitment. For any organization to be successful, having commitment of employees has a paramount importance. The analysis shows that coworker relation, pay, personality and promotion have a positive impact on Employee Commitment and organizations should maintain the socialization factor in workplace for better commitment to employees. In conclusion, the major findings shows that Socialization has a positive and significant impact on Employee Commitment in K Electric.

Limitations

Following are the limitations that was faced while conducting the results.

1. This study focuses on only four variables that effects employee commitment.
2. There were in aggregate of three hundred and seventy-one conveyed to the research.
3. The after effects of the study are constrained to the two main factors of human resource management which are socialization and employee commitment.

Recommendation

Based on the findings following recommendations are providing

1. This study recommended that management should consistently major and evaluate the commitment of employees, through that they maintain high performance from the employees.
2. The organization should exhibit to its employee a high level of commitment.
3. Theworkers would be given advocate capitals, services, trading autonomy, and strengthen responsibility to the assurance of employees in the organization.

Areas For Future Research

This study only focuses on four variables, therefore there is a scope for other researchers to identify the other factors that may affect employee commitment which are not studying before. This study was limited to one organization (K electric). Future researchers can do this research to different sectors.

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